

STAKEHOLDERS

- Citizens and civil society
- Farmers and their associations
- Municipalities, regional authorities
- Drinking water utilities
- Tourism sector, anglers
- Hydropower plants

CHALLENGES

- Seasonal or periodical **water extremities** (floods, droughts)
- **Allocation of water resources** among competing uses

AMBITION

- Test an **improved water and landscape management methodology**, based on the resources and technical results of the project, especially **comprehensive information** on competitive water uses
- Implement a multi-stakeholders conflict resolution process, towards policy realization

INN WATER PARTNERS

A **consortium** gathering 13 organisations (Research and Technology Organisations, SMEs, end users, associations with EU and international coverages).

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INN WATER

Promoting
social innovation
to renew
multi-level and cross-sector
water governance

Pilot Site #5 MIDDLE TISZA Hungary

Led by

Middle Tisza Region
Water Directorate

REKK LLC

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MIDDLE TISZA

The pilot site is located in the flat region of the Tisza River Basin in the middle of the Hungarian Great plain. The pilot area gets water from the Lake Tisza. The size of the area is 2,900 km².

METHOD

1. Set the composition of pilot site community
2. Assess the current water governance situation
3. Set objectives and planning
4. Test and implement schemes and tools
5. Feedback and assessment

5 PILOT SITES

Implementing different types of governance mechanisms and covering different **water challenges**, test and co-develop the tools and methods.

INN WATER
Pilot Site Community

France, Réunion Island - **Economic focus**

Italy, Middle Brenta Basin - **Ecosystem services & Drinking water sector**

Spain, Figueres - **Water scarcity**

United Kingdom, West Country - **Water quality**

Hungary, Middle Tisza - **Water allocation**

